

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

2 June 2023

Screening: Love Will Change The Earth, Directed by Reyhan Tuvi, 2014

This documentary narrates how people from very diverse lifestyles and ideologies fought together to convert the Gezi Park-the only remaining green area in the centre of the city- into a model of the world they dreamed of.

Q&A Session with Ayşe Çavdar and Diren Demir, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy

Ayşe Çavdar completed her BA degree in Journalism at Ankara University and received her MA in History at Boğaziçi University in Turkey. She finalised her doctoral thesis titled "The Loss of Modesty: The Adventure of Muslim Family from Neighborhood to Gated Community" at the European University of Viadrina in 2014 (supported by the Global Prayers Project initiated by MetroZones). She was a postdoctoral fellow at Käte Hamburger Kolleg - Center for Global Cooperation Research in Duisburg in 2017. She continued her studies as a visiting scholar at Philipps University in Marburg for two years between 2018-2020. Recently, she has been a visiting scholar at Bard College Berlin. Alongside her academic career, Çavdar has been a journalist for three decades, working on diverse political, cultural, and social issues. She participated in and worked for different NGOs in Turkey professionally and as a volunteer. Her current academic interests include urban and religious studies focusing particularly on middle-class living spaces and religious performativities. Recently, her work centred on two new topics. The first one is the nationalist and religious symbolization of the state as an idea(l) and effect. Second, is the focus on the new secularities rising among the youths in Turkey. These research interests are linked closely with the political manifestations of authoritarianism in Turkey. She co-edited two books: with Volkan Aytar, *Media and Security Sector Oversight, Limits and Possibilities*, TESEV, 2009; With Pelin Tan, *The State of Exception in an Exceptional City*, Sel Yayınları, 2013.

Diren Demir (Istanbul, 1997) is an interdisciplinary artist and independent curator. Demir's work seeks transformative solutions to the challenges posed by patriarchal and authoritarian regimes. Demir's installations and performances frequently deal with revelation and the body-power relationship as a site of conflict. Demir focuses on transformational activism, participatory practices and developing new models of resistance in their artworks. Demir's work includes queer themes, using their own body to challenge stereotypical gender positions and de-gender memories of place and the city by referring to LGBTIQ+ history in their articles, seminars and workshops. In 2019, their compilation titled "A Night of June: A Biographical Analysis of the Stonewall Revolution" was published. In August 2022, their new poetry and illustration book "Hail to the Fallen" took its place in bookstores. Demir has curated more than 30 guerrilla exhibitions on streets and rural areas, putting

the accessibility of art at the forefront, as well as in places such as Akbank Art and Gazhane Museum. Their works and projects were exhibited in many different countries such as Estonia, Turkey, Serbia, Netherlands, Germany, India...

Audience: I want to ask everyone to think for themselves what the Gezi spirit truly means. We have been talking about this Gezi spirit for the last 10 years, but how has it guided us and helped us become better people? How has it fostered solidarity with groups that are faring worse than us? In Turkey, the Gezi movement was a crucial period where previously non-politicized groups became more involved and aware of the issues happening around them. The Kurdish, LGBT, Feminist, and Socialist movements have long been pillars of the Turkish social struggle, and Gezi opened up the space for many urban, secular, and middle-class groups to join the struggle. However, when I reflect on the decade after Gezi, I can't help but feel anger and disappointment. In 2015-6-7, peaceful protests were brutally shut down, and many lives were lost. The world should have stopped and paid attention to what was happening in Turkey, but it didn't. Instead, the concept of Gezi spirit seems to have been co-opted and fetishized, reduced to a month of symbolic solidarity and pilgrimage, where people participated, learned about solidarity, and then returned to their normal lives. I feel let down by the urban middle class who seem to have gone back to their routines without enacting lasting change. I don't mean to point fingers, but I can't help but be cynical when I hear the term "Gezi spirit" being used in such a way. It feels like it's diminishing the impact and potential of the beautiful movement that was supposed to open the door to positive change and close the doors of injustice. Thank you, and I apologise for being cynical.

ŞE: Thanks for your comment. I just would like to introduce Ayşe Çavdar before letting her respond. Ayşe Hoca is an anthropologist and journalist, and she is currently a visiting scholar at the Bard College in Berlin. I have been following Ayşe Çavdar's work on Medyascope for many many years. For those of you who speak Turkish I recommend her programmes there.

AÇ: I don't (laughing ensues)

ŞE: Her take on developments, her passion and her care is something I connect with everytime I hear her speak and that is why my co-curator and I wanted to invite her to speak following this film. She is a researcher and very knowledgeable on Turkey's middle class, religious performativities, gated communities, so I'll leave the microphone to you.

AÇ: Thank you very much. What was important in Gezi was the dignity of all people, the dignity of citizenship. In the film, there is a scene where a man from Diyarbakır expresses his surprise at what was happening in Gezi, and he explains why he and others from different backgrounds came together there. They came to make their struggles known and to show that they too are citizens. Gezi didn't start because of

"a couple of trees" or a park, but it began as an occupation to protect the park from urban transformation plans. People from Istanbul Technical University initially occupied the park based on misinformation about the park's fate. They stayed in tents in the park. They were urban planning students. I was living in Kurtuluş at that time, so it was my neighborhood, and I was also there with those youngsters. Police violence against the students was brutal. It was unbelievable. I hadn't seen something like that before, and I've been a journalist since 1992. In Ankara as well! I mean, it was unbelievable. So people came there to protect the students. The students were protecting the park that belongs to the people and the public. So everybody remembered: "Oh yeah, we are citizens..." This city belongs to us and those students are protecting what belongs to us, and that's why the police we are paying for with our taxes are killing them there, putting their tents on fire... Gezi was this: it was not a spirit. It was a fact. We are citizens, and that park belongs to us, and what happened? Thanks to the state, we remembered that we are citizens. Gezi became a place of togetherness and a utopian experiment with much kindness. People from different backgrounds, some of whom didn't like each other, were protecting something together. Gezi also brought attention to the urban transformation happening in other areas of Istanbul, such as Tarlabaşı, and the feeling that the city was being stolen from its people. Tarlabaşı was in the centre of the city, but it was still distant because nobody we know was living there; it belonged to the "outsiders" of the city - migrants, prostitutes, trans people, "gypsies"... I know it well because I lived in Tarlabaşı too. I lived everywhere in Istanbul, I should say, because I was a poor journalist, most of this time unemployed; that's why I was living in all those neighbourhoods. The state was horrified by Gezi because citizens were demanding something beyond what the state wanted to give them. It was about togetherness, commonality, and equality, which scared the state. The Gezi spirit, if it can be called that, reemerged during the 2015 elections when the ruling party lost for the first time. Sırrı Süreyya Önder, a film director but also a deputy of the HDP, was also there during the first days of Gezi, with the students. Whereas Selahattin Demirtaş at that time wasn't because he cared so much about the peace process between Kurds and the State, that's why he was trying to keep a distance from Gezi. However, Sırrı Süreyya Önder launched himself in front of the bulldozers, and then these Kemalist ladies saw that and they voted for the HDP in the cities. That raised the HDP's votes to 13% during the 2015 elections. People started building political solidarity after experiencing solidarity in the parks during Gezi. However, today, even in opposition alliances, there is reluctance to mention Gezi to avoid scaring some voters - Erdoğan's 50%. Nevertheless, Gezi is still there, a revolutionary fact that determines the context and content of Turkish politics. After Gezi, people realised the beauty and dignity of being citizens together. Even groups that would normally hate each other, like TGB (Turkish Youth Association) and HDP (People's Democratic Party), defended the same park during Gezi. The longing for that sense of citizenship is what drives the opposition against the government and oppositionary parties, who should embrace and acknowledge the significance of Gezi.

ŞE: Thank you Ayşe for that brief overview of the dynamics on the ground and providing your take on what the Gezi Spirit is.

I would also like to introduce our second guest who is with us this evening. Diren Demir, I am sure you recognise them, they were part of Reyhan Tuvî's film as a 15-year-old... Today they are an interdisciplinary artist, who is now based in Berlin, and an independent curator as well. Their work actually focuses on trying to find solutions to problems posed by patriarchal and authoritarian regimes. Diren, we would love to hear

from you. Can you tell us how you met Reyhan, and how your mother allowed you to go to the park at that age... I mean, I was 27 and my parents were trying to prevent me from being there...

DD: That's interesting. I remember being there on the 28th of May. I had seen the news and felt that this couldn't happen in my reality, so I instinctively went there. Initially, I was there for the trees, but I was faced with police violence and found refuge in a Chinese restaurant, without telling my mother. One day, during the first or second week of June, police violence was at its peak, and they were chasing people out of Taksim Square. In the middle of the empty square, there was just one scared dog, and they began spraying pepper gas again. I pushed the policemen, ran after the dog, and cleaned its eyes. The dog started playing with me, and I took it inside a nearby shop. That's when Reyhan Tuvi approached me and learned my name was "Diren," which means "Resistance" in Turkish. It was a serendipitous meeting that led to my involvement in the documentary. Reyhan Tuvi's approach to documentaries was intimate and engaging. She didn't exoticize me or the other participants but genuinely wanted to know us better. She established relationships with us, including our families, and the interviews were conducted at a later date when we could reflect back on our experiences during Gezi. She really engaged with me and my family.

She came to my house, she met my mother and all my aunts, she invited my family for wine one night at her place. She did the same with all other participants. She really engaged with my life and wanted to know me more.

ŞE: I guess she was obviously able to keep the relationship going because the interviews that you gave in the film were made after Gezi so how did that develop? From what I know, Reyhan didn't really have a plan when she started filming in the park, she just knew she needed to be there as a journalist and a documentarian with her camera, and I think she then found all her protagonists. The interviews were conducted at a much later date so you were kind of reflecting back. Can you tell us how that developed?

DD: As I remember, we were always in touch. I also had the chance to meet all the other protagonists of the film. I remember that there was more than 70 hours of footage and that is quite a concrete part of what she should have, and that was the process. I think it was the same year and still very fresh and I was still 15.

ŞE: Maybe just before opening up the floor Ayşe, I would like to ask you about the anti-capitalist Muslims that we see in the film, since you have done so much research with conservative families and communities in Turkey, and you spoke about being a citizen and remembering what it means to be a citizen - requesting and asking for your rights, but can you open up the ground as to why the anti-capitalist Muslims were there and what was appealing about Gezi that made more conservative folk also show up?

AÇ: Actually, they were there before everybody. Yeryüzü Sofrası (The Earth Tables) started in 2011 in Gezi Park. It wasn't the anti-capitalist Muslims but the Labour and Justice Initiative - all of them are Muslim people and youngsters coming from very, very religious families. They started Iftar (breaking the fast) during Ramadan in 2011 to protest the luxury hotel iftars organised by the pro-AKP businesspeople. They started there. In 2011, there was also an artist collective there against the government's plans regarding Gezi. Somehow they united. Anti-capitalist Muslims were a little more crowded than the Labour and Justice Initiative, but more or less the same kind of people, let's say. They were there before everybody. Their concern was more about the content of religiosity. They are still believers, even today. In the 1990s, I was partly like that; I was calling myself a Muslim anarchist. Still, I believe Mohammed was a revolutionary guy until he moved to Medina. Before Medina, he was a really good guy for me because he was revolutionising a sort of tribal law ruling Mecca in a very brutal way. What was happening in Mecca at that time was the corruption of the Abrahamic religion. So the anti-capitalist Muslims are saying the same thing; they say the AKP is corrupting Islam, so we should reclaim our religion from them. How? To be together with those people oppressed by the state, by the AKP government, that's why it merged over there. I should say: one of the first and biggest attacks in the Gezi Park happened on a Thursday, just before Friday

(a holy day in Islam). It was very important because on that Thursday the anti-capitalist Muslims made a call all over Istanbul to do the Friday prayer in Gezi Park. The government was manipulating people saying: ah, they are drinking alcohol there, they are smoking hash, etc. But if the general public would see: ah, they are also praying Namaz over there, Gezi Park would somehow have been sacralized, I think. It would be untouchable afterwards. Therefore, right after that call for the Friday prayer, that evening there was a huge attack. It wasn't only the AKP government; it was the state bureaucracy too. At that time they did not work like they do now. There was still a sort of distance between the government and the state security bureaucracy. The security bureaucracy too had approved AKP's move because the state apparatus also does not want secular and religious criticism against how the state is acting. It is a traditional Turkish state - they use religious people against secular, secular against religious if they feel threatened by the citizens. So they also approved what the AKP was planning, and that Thursday was really unbelievable. Another thing: thankfully they were there. Religious society still has some respect from secularist society; whoever represented this in the Gezi Park gained some sort of respect because everybody knows - even Erdoğan knows very well - what happened in Gezi Park wasn't the mistake of the people; they were right, and there, the unjust side in that composition was him and the state. Everybody knows that. That's why thanks to Gezi Park, although they are trying to use this polarisation in society and whatnot, through religiosity and secularity, secularism vs Islamism, Kurds vs Turks, and so on, it doesn't actually work. Due to this, they have to push it that much. If it would work, they wouldn't need to push it, but they are, like hell! Thanks to the Yeryüzü Sofrası (The Earth Tables), Islam still has a sort of civic respect from people. At least, I can feel that strictly secular people can distinguish that there are different types of Islam, e.g., that the anti-capitalist Muslims are another type of Islam than that of the government. Since then there is a sort of secularisation from below in conservative families. For 4 years now, I have been undertaking digital ethnographic research with young women - there are thousands of them - who are exposed to violence from their families because they do not want to wear the veil anymore. When I say violence, I am not only referring to physical violence. They are using psychiatric drugs to convince those young women to wear the veil. There are psychiatrists in Turkey specialised in this issue, for example. I am speaking about very sophisticated violence. It started with Gezi. When I listen to them, they don't mention Gezi, and they are claiming another type of Islam. They want to unveil, but they do not want to leave Islam behind. They say another Islam is possible, and that is also coming from those stories of Gezi.

ŞE: Does anyone have any questions? ... Diren, I was thinking about one of the last sentences that you say in the film about your politics being "love". Obviously you were 15 then, now you are 25, you're an artist, you don't live in Turkey anymore, and you live here. I was just wondering how Gezi shaped your artistic journey, your creative process. Does it have a role in that in any way, has it been this important mark for you politically and is it coming through artistically?

DD: Beyond shaping my political and artistic journey, what Gezi did for me, I believe, is that it revealed my true self. It didn't shape me, but rather revealed who I am. It was a remarkably non-judgmental place, where I could be authentic and face the reality of our culture. At this point, I am deeply interested in creating temporary autonomous zones, greatly inspired by Hakim Bey. Through performance and by using my body, I

attempt to create temporary autonomous zones in the city and public spaces, reclaiming them for self-expression. What I realized at Gezi Park was that we belong to that place and it belongs to us. Gezi itself was an attempt at squatting. The concept of squats spread to many places - including Atatürk Cultural Centre and numerous streets and corners across the country. Even after the Gezi protests in Istanbul, we witnessed many squats in various areas of Turkey. I also participated in the Don Quixote Squat in Yeldeğirmeni. We truly kept that culture alive.

Q: I have a question for Diren. It is not a coincidence to have you here in Germany. There is this sociological phenomenon that young people keep on leaving Turkey. I think the numbers are significant. I studied at the German School in Istanbul and in my time, less than 10% of the graduates would go to Germany or German-speaking countries. Right now, there is not even 10% remaining in Turkey. I wanted to ask you, what happened with this sense of optimism or pessimism in relation to the engagement with this country?

DD: Thank you very much. It's not precisely about Germany, I just felt like I needed to get away from that country. I define my existence here, or anywhere outside of Turkey, as self-exile, as a Kurdish Alawite and queer person, I felt all the violence of the authoritarian regime, directly in my body. I was very, very anxious being there. That's why I would say. What happened with optimism? I try to keep it alive as much as possible. I still resist and stand against every kind of authoritarian approach and I hope I will continue doing it in a stronger way.

ŞE: From the previous panel, right before the film screenings, Zeynep Gambetti said that resistance is a humanitarian duty so you have different ways of resisting but there was just this sentence at the beginning of the film, in a scene taking place during a forum, where a young girl says: "I was thinking of leaving Turkey and then Gezi happened, and now I'm here to stay." Ever since Sunday, I have been hearing this sentence a lot from Turkey.

AÇ: Gezi gave us a reason to love the country. That's the hope. Generally, I am a hopeful person, but after this election, it's not very easy, and I'm just thinking and thinking. I am totally hopeless about institutional politics. But I believe in society, and society showed its power with 48% for an Alawite presidential candidate (Kemal Kılıçdaroğlu). For Turkey, that's a big deal, but even today, we are listening to the discussion among the different deputies of the CHP (the main opposition party of Turkey), and they are discussing how many thousands of polling boxes they couldn't attend to... Almost 20,000 equates to 2.5 million votes! For me, I am rejecting this right now. Maybe it's because of the stages of mourning; my country is my emotional issue after all. In recent years, I don't actually have any other emotional issues. I reject the fact that we lost the election. I think society won the election, but institutional politics could not keep up with it. There is still a reason to hope for something better, and that is because Gezi happened. What I miss in Turkey is Gezi. Not the park - it's actually very small and not very beautiful... It was on my way to my office when I was working for a publishing house, and we were publishing books and encyclopaedias about rakı. So every morning and evening, I was going through Gezi, and it would take 3.5 minutes. That's the park. Gezi gave us a reason to love the country. It's not about hope. Gezi did not stay there - except in my hometown, Bayburt - in every city of Turkey, Gezi happened. One more story - one of the

advisors of Tayyip Erdoğan at that time was a very old friend of mine from my anarchist Muslim times. Of course, he was siding with the power, and I with the anarchists. He invited me to talk about Gezi; I will not say his name. He started asking me questions about who is organising and who is behind the protests... I said: look at me, who in Turkey has that power (and he comes from the conservative labour union background), do you know anyone in Turkey who has the power to organise that and country-wide, do you believe that? He said: I am now with the state rationale, and I just responded: what? Gezi gave us that kind of belief - yes, we can; yes, we are here. We learned something. It was about citizenship, and this was the Spirit of Gezi. I have the right, according to the constitution. That is citizenship. We need a country now.

ŞE: Thank you all...

The series GeZinema was created in collaboration with the H2020 MSCA-IF project, VIDEOACT, a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101025524.

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